

CarE-Service

**Circular economy business models
for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through
advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services**

Data Policy and Management Plan Second version

(Deliverable 9.7)

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Project Consortium

CNR	<i>Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche</i>	Italy
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ENV	<i>Envirobat Espana SI</i>	Spain
PROD	<i>Prodigentia Information Technology S.A.</i>	Portugal
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COBSER	<i>Cobat Servizi</i>	Italy
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Fraunhofer	<i>Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V.</i>	Germany
AVIC	<i>Avicenne Developpement</i>	France
CIA	<i>CIA Automation and Robotics s.r.l.</i>	Italy
EVAI	<i>E-Vai s.r.l.</i>	Italy
JRC	<i>JRC - Joint Research Centre European Commission</i>	Belgium

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the first updated version of the deliverable D9.4 with title “Data Policy and Management plan – First version”. The deliverable D9.4 was submitted in M6 of the project (November 2018) by C-ECO. In this document, the changes that have taken place during this period (from M6 to M18) will be mentioned. This document will be the only valid Data Policy and Management Plan after its submission on November 29, 2019.

The deliverable aims at establishing the policy framework for information management and confidentiality within the CarE-Service consortium, the members of the Consumers’ and Stakeholders Committees, as well as external stakeholders. The policy framework for data management includes principles ensuring the effective management and confidentiality of data, information and records throughout the related authorities and responsibilities. The main purpose of the data/information management policy is to protect both electronic and paper-version of data/information from any unauthorized use and access with a clear role and responsibilities of those who manage the data/information, while ensuring the greatest possible access of data/information, consistent with legislation and relevant EU/consortium policies. Detailed information will be provided on the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation.

This deliverable includes the Data Management Plan (DMP) as part of the Open Data Pilot initiative. In particular, the deliverable includes:

- The procedures and criteria that are used to identify/recruit research participants, as well as the informed consent procedures that are implemented for the participation of humans and for the collection, storage, and protection of personal data (in response to Ethics Requirement 1);
- detailed information on the procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction, and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation (in response to Ethics Requirement 3).

This deliverable includes open research data policy, that follows the guidelines provided by the Commission.

This is the second version of the document, and as it is known for the first version, this document will be updated during the project lifetime, whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to):

- new data,
- changes in consortium policies (e.g. new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent),
- changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g. new consortium members joining or old members leaving).

The next planned updated version of the deliverable will be submitted the 36th month of the project (May 2021). The first version of the report for the DMP was submitted in November 2018. This updated version focuses on the definition of the data that the partners generates during the project period from M1 to M18.

List of Acronyms

AVIC	Avicenne Development
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CECO	Circular Economy Solutions GmbH
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire - European Organization for Nuclear Research
CIA	CIA Automations and Robotics SRL
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerch
COBSE	COBAT, Consorzio Nazionale Raccoltae Riciclo
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas
DM	Data Management
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
ENV	ENVIROBAT Espana SL
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
EVAI	E-VAI SRL
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FCA	FIAT CHRYSLER Automobiles Italy S.p.A.
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMA	IMA Materialforschung und Anwendungstechnik GmbH
IP	Internet Protocol
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JRC	JRC – Joint Research Centre European Commission
LIU	Linkopings Universitet
N/A	Not applicable
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PROD	PRODIGENTIA – Technologias de Informacao SA
RAD	RADICI Novacips S.p.A.

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1. Introduction

This report describes the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the CarE-Service Project. The report aims at establishing the policy framework for information management and confidentiality within the CarE-Service consortium, the members of the Consumers' and Stakeholders Committees, as well as external stakeholders. The policy framework for data management includes principles ensuring the effective management and confidentiality of data, information and records throughout the related authorities and responsibilities. The main purpose of the data/information management policy is to protect both electronic and paper-version of data/information from any unauthorized use and access with a clear role and responsibilities of those who manage the data/information, while ensuring the greatest possible access of data/information, consistent with legislation and relevant EU/consortium policies. Detailed information is provided on the procedures that are implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national (eg. Bundesdatenschutzgesetz (BDSG) for Germany) and EU legislation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation)).

The DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by CarE-Service Horizon 2020 project. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), the DMP includes information on:

- the handling of research data during & after the end of the project,
- what data are collected, processed and/or generated,
- which methodology & standards are applied,
- whether data are shared/made open access and,
- how data are curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

2. Data policy – General and personal data protection

During the project data are collected from or generated by several sources. For research purposes, CarE-Service project may contain and process personal data from various sources (e.g. interviews, questionnaires, online ICT platforms and websites, etc.). Additionally, personal data of the project participants may be collected during meetings, workshops, on social media platforms etc. in the form of photos, videos, names, etc., for research, promotion or other purposes of the project. “Personal data” means information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person.

An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person, Article 4 EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Examples: name, address, identification number, pseudonym, occupation, e-mail, location data, Internet Protocol (IP) address, cookie ID, phone number, data provided by smart meters, etc.

Individuals are not considered “identifiable” if identifying them requires excessive effort.

Completely anonymized data does not fall under the data privacy rules (from the moment it has been completely anonymized).

“Processing of personal data” means any operation (or set of operations) performed on personal data, either manually or by automatic means. This includes:

- collection (digital audio recording, digital video caption, etc.)
- recording
- organization, structuring & storage (cloud, LAN or WAN servers)
- adaptation or alteration (merging sets, amplification, etc.)
- retrieval & consultation
- use
- disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available (share, exchange, transfer)
- alignment or combination
- restriction, erasure or destruction.

Examples: access to/consultation of a database containing personal data; managing of the database; posting/putting a photo of a person on a website; storing IP addresses or MAC addresses; video recording (CCTV); creating a mailing list or a list of participants.

Processing normally covers any action that uses data for research purposes (even if interviewees, human volunteers, patients, etc. are not actively included in the research).

Personal data may come from any type of research activity (ICT research), personal records (financial, criminal, education, etc.), lifestyle and health information, physical characteristics, gender and ethnic background, location tracking and domicile information, etc.

All research processes and all the project activities (meetings, publications, etc.) for the CarE-Service project must comply with ethical principles and all the applicable international, EU and national law (in particular the GDPR, national data protection laws and other relevant legislation).

2.1 Pre-screening

For the first stage, there is a pre-screening process of personal data. The one who collects the data must be able to answer the following questions and to act properly with the following instructions.

1. Does your research involve processing of personal data? If yes, in that case the partner must provide detailed information such as:

- Details of the technical and organizational measures to safeguard the rights of the research participants.
- Details of the informed consent procedures.
- Details of the security measures to prevent unauthorized access to personal data.
- Details of “data minimization principle” (processing only relevant data and limiting the processing to the purpose of the project).
- Details of the anonymization /pseudonymization techniques.
- Justification in case research data will not be anonymized/ pseudonymized (if relevant).
- Details of the data transfers (type of data transferred and country to which it is transferred – for both EU and non-EU countries).

Additionally, documents should be kept on file, such as Informed Consent Forms and Information Sheets used (if relevant) (D10.1).

In case that the research involves processing of personal data, the partner should be able to reply to the following question(s) and to act properly with the following instructions.

2. Does it involve the processing of special categories of personal data (e.g. genetic, health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)?

In that case the partner must provide detailed information such as:

- Justification for the processing of special categories of personal data.
- Justification in case research objects will not be anonymized/ pseudonymized (if applicable)

3. Does it involve processing of genetic, biometric or health data?

A declaration confirming compliance with the laws of the country where the data was collected should be kept on file.

4. Does it involve profiling, systematic monitoring of individuals or processing of large scale of special categories of data, intrusive methods of data processing (such as tracking, surveillance, audio and video recording, geolocation tracking etc.) or any other data processing operation that may result in high risk to the rights and freedoms of the research participants?

In that case the partner must provide detailed information such as:

- Details of the methods used for tracking, surveillance or observation of participants.
- Details of the methods used for profiling.
- Risk assessment for the data processing activities.
- Details of safeguarding the rights of the research participants.

- Details on the procedures for informing the research participants about profiling, and its possible consequences and the protection measures.

Data protection impact assessment (art. 35 GDPR) must be provided.

5. Does your research involve further processing of previously collected personal data (including use of preexisting data sets or sources, merging existing data sets)?

In that case the partner must provide detailed information such as:

- Details of the database used or of the source of the data.
- Details of the data processing operations.
- Details of safeguarding the rights of the research participants.
- Details of “data minimization principle” (processing only relevant data and limiting the processing to the purpose of the project).
- Justification in case research objects will not be anonymized/ pseudonymized (if applicable)

Additionally, documents should be kept on file, such as 1) Declaration confirming lawful basis for the data processing, 2) Permission by the owner/manager of the data sets (e.g. social media databases) (if applicable), 3) Informed Consent Forms + Information Sheets + other consent documents (opt in processes, etc.) (if applicable).

6. Does your research involve publicly available data?

In that case the partner must confirm that the data used in the project is publicly available and can be freely used for the project.

Additionally, documents should be kept on file, such as permission by the owner/manager of the data sets (e.g. social media databases) (if applicable).

7. Is it planned to export personal data from the EU to non-EU countries? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved.

In that case the partner must provide detailed information such as the details of the types of personal data to be exported. Also, the details of safeguarding the rights of the research participants must be described.

Additionally, documents should be kept on file, such as a declaration of confirming compliance with Chapter V of the GDPR.

8. Is it planned to import personal data from non-EU countries into the EU? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved.

In that case the partner must provide detailed information such as the details of the types of personal data to be imported.

Additionally, documents should be kept on file, such as a declaration of confirming compliance with the laws of the country in which the data was collected.

2.2 Risk analysis for all data processing activities

All single processing activities of personal data must be listed in overview (independent from criticality of the personal data). The list must be created, maintained and updated by the data controller.

The overview will be the basis for the risk analysis.

For all processing activities of personal data, the following information is required:

- Processing activity
- Description of the processing activity
- Data Types and contained data (e.g. personal data, financial data, working data, ...)
- Legal basis for the processing activity
- Responsible of the processing activity (Person, Position, Company)
- Purpose of the processing activity
- Affected parties of the processing activity
- Criticality of the processing activity (in terms of confidentiality, availability and integrity)
- Deletion period of the processing activity

On each processing activity the risk analysis must be applied.

Following details need to be described and evaluated:

- Risk description (e.g. unauthorized access to personal data)
- Potential harm for affected party
- Description of technical and organizational measures
- Classification of risk in dependency on probability and severity of risk (e.g. low, medium, high, ...)
- Risk handling (e.g. accept risk, moderate or eliminate risk probability by implementing additional measures, ...)
- Re-classification of risk in dependency on probability and severity of risk (e.g. low, medium, high, ...) in case additional measures will be implemented.

2.3 Anonymization and pseudonymization

Under these rules, all the collected personal data must be processed in accordance with certain principles and conditions that aim to limit the negative impact on the persons concerned and ensure fairness, transparency and accountability of the data processing, data quality and confidentiality. As described in Deliverable 10.1, CarE-Service does not intend to collect, store and/or process sensitive data (health, genetic or biometric data). CarE-Service may collect, store and monitor both “anonymous” and “non-anonymous” non-sensitive personal data.

This implies the following main obligations for all the participants:

- Data processing should be subject to appropriate safeguards.
- Data should, wherever possible, be processed in anonymized or pseudonymized form (D10.1, Chapter 2).
- Data processing is subject to free and fully informed consent of the persons concerned (unless already covered by another legal basis, e.g. legitimate or public interest).
- Data processing must NOT be performed in secret and research participants must be made aware that they take part in a research project and be informed of their rights and the potential risks that the data processing may bring.
- Data may be processed ONLY if it is really adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the research ('data minimization principle').

Collection of personal data (e.g. on religion, sexual orientation, race, ethnicity, etc.) is not essential and relevant with the scope of the research and the project, therefore the collection of sensitive personal data is not permitted.

It is recommended all participants or partners use anonymized or pseudonymized data for project purposes.

“Anonymized” means that the data has been rendered anonymous in such a way that the data subject can no longer be identified (and therefore is no longer personal data and thus outside the scope of data protection laws).

Figure 1: Anonymization (Source: www.wso2.com, 2018)

Anonymization also helps in making research data and project results FAIR, without providing personal data (Figure 2) (FAIR: see Chapter 6).

Figure 2: Anonymization of personal data (Source: OpenAIRE, 2017)

“Pseudonymized” means to divide the data from its direct identifiers so that linkage to a person is only possible with additional information that is held separately. The additional information must be kept separately and securely from processed data to ensure non-attribution.

Figure 3: Pseudonymization, (Source: www.wso2.com, 2018)

It is recommended to involve the data protection officer (DPO) in all stages of the project whenever data privacy issues arise.

Even if all privacy-related issues are addressed, research data may still raise other ethics issues, such as the potential misuse of the research methodology/ findings or ethics harms to specific groups.

2.4 Social Media Policy

Social media communities has been created in different social media platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter) as part of the dissemination activities of CarE-Service project that encourages self-expression and mirrors the values and the scope of CarE-Service project including respect for the rights, dignity, and property of others. All partners, followers, group members are asked to do their part to help project achieve the goal. In doing that, partners are kindly asked not to post content that:

- is threatening, abusive, obscene, indecent, or objectionable;
- is confidential as it is described in the Grant Agreement or includes sensitive for the project or a partner information, deceptive, false, or misleading;
- violates the intellectual property rights of other people or partners;
- is illegal and does not comply with regional or international legislation e.g. GDPR or other;
- is self-promoting spam;
- is inappropriate, offensive, or hateful.

Sharing pictures, videos, recordings or any other information without the permission of the appeared persons is not permitted either. Consent form from the appeared persons must be signed and kept on record (see §9).

The admin of the accounts reserves the right to remove any content or block users that violate community's guidelines, or that the admin determines are otherwise offensive to the community. All content must also comply with Facebook's, Twitter's, and LinkedIn's policies as well.

As users, partners can visit, join, follow, "like" project's social media. Further information on how social platforms handle personal data as users could be found in the links below:

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/legal/privacy-policy>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/privacy/explanation>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/en/privacy>

3. Data summary

The main purpose for the data collection/generation of the CarE-Service project is for the description of new circular economy business models in innovative hybrid and electric mobility through advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services.

The CarE-Service project will produce several datasets during the lifetime of the project. All the data which will be collected will be relevant to the purposes of the projects, such as the establishment of circular economy business models, the development of the Smart Mobile Modules, the creation of customer-driven products and the development and validation of technical solutions for reused, remanufactured and recycled components and the evaluation of these business models through demonstration and life cycle assessment (LCA).

All the collected or generated data will be analyzed and evaluated from a range of methodological perspectives for project development and engineering and scientific purposes.

A range of data has been created during the project and new data will be created in the next months. These data are available in a variety of easily accessible formats, including Documents (Word) (DOCX), Spreadsheets (Excel) (XLSX, CSV), Presentation files (Power Point) (PPT), PostScript (PDF, XPS), images, audio and video files (JPEG, PNG, GIF, TIFF, WAV, MPEG, AIFF, OGG, AVI, MP4), Technical CAD drawings (DWG), Origin (OPJ), compressed formats (TAR.GZ, MTZ), Program database (PDB, DBS, MDF, NDF), open-standard file format (JSON) etc.

The following table contains all the datasets that have been generated from the beginning of the project till the month 18.

For every dataset which has been generated for a task, the leading partner of the task is the Master of Data. The Master of Data is responsible for the collection of the data from the other partners, the file and sharing actions among the consortium, the creation of the linked metadata files and also the activities for publishing the data, e.g. on Zenodo platform.

Datasets from M1 (June 2018) to M18 (November 2019) of the project

Description/ Name of the datasets	Type (Deliverable, publication, survey, paper, etc.)	D	Format	Dissemination level (public or confidential)	Repository	Availability since/ from:	Master of Data
Data Policy and Management Plan – First Version	Deliverable	9.4	PDF, DOCX	Public	Zenodo, Project SharePoint, C-ECO internal	01.09.2019	C-ECO
Design of Car-E Service logistics – Final Version	Deliverable	6.1	PDF DOCX	Public	COBSER, Project SharePoint, Zenodo	30.05.2019	COBSER
Dissemination and Communication Plan –First Version	Deliverable	8.2	PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, CSIC Internal	31/05/19	CSIC
Detailed engineering of processes and technologies for techno-polymers re-use and recycling solutions	Deliverable	5.3	PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, CSIC Internal	30/06/19	CSIC
How to recycle an electric vehicle (in Spanish)	Divulcation paper	N/A	PDF	Public	Zenodo, CSIC Internal	19/01/2019	CSIC
Lithium-ion batteries towards circular economy: a literature review of opportunities and issues of recycling treatments	Conference paper	N/A	PDF	Public	CSIC Internal	04/06/2019	CNR, ENV, CSIC
POPD - H Requirement No. 2	Deliverable	10.1	Folder of PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal (office and online)	01.06.2018	CNR
Collected Signed Consent Forms	Paper and Scan versions of forms	10.1	Folders of PDF, DOCs, JPGs, PAPERS	Confidential	Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal (office and online)	01.06.2018	CNR
Project Management Handbook	Deliverable	9.1	Folder of PDF, DOCX, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.06.2018	CNR
Meeting Minutes and Notes	Depository	9.2	Folders of PDF, DOCX, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Internal CNR SharePoint	01.06.2018	CNR
Management Report	Deliverable	9.2	Folder of PDF, DOCX, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.06.2018	CNR

Financial Reports	Deliverable	9.2	Folder of PDF, DOCX, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR Internal	01.06.2018	CNR
WP and Task Progress Reports	Deliverable	9.2	Folder of PDF, DOCX, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.06.2018	CNR
Project website	Website	8.1	Folder of PDF, JPG, DOCX	Public	Online at www.careservice.eu , CNR internal, Project Sharepoint	01.06.2018	CNR
Requirements for innovative services and business models (This deliverable is lead by LiU, but CNR contributed substantially to the contents. Since some content of the deliverable is solely in possession of CNR, this dataset is stated in addition to the D1.1 with master data of LiU).	Deliverable	1.1	Folder of PDF, DOCX, MP4, PPT, ELSX	Public	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.06.2018	CNR
Survey Design and Collected Data (This survey is lead by LiU and is pulic on LiU dataset, but CNR contributed to the design of it and deposit a version of collected data driven from LiU platform. This is why this dataset is stated in addition to the D1.1 with master data of LiU).	Survey	1.1	Folder of PDF, DOCX, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.06.2018	CNR
Interview Recordings and/or transcripts (This task is lead by LiU, but CNR conducted some of its interviews alone, thus, this dataset is stated in addition to the D1.1 with master data of LiU)	Interview	1.1	Folder of PDF, DOCX, MP4, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.06.2018	CNR
Co-design of customized mobility services and business models (B2C) (This deliverable is lead by EVAI, but CNR contributed substantially to the contents. Since some content of the deliverable or files related to the deliverable is managed by CNR, this dataset is stated in addition to the D2.1 with master data of EVAI)	Deliverable	2.1	Folder of PDF, DOCX, MP4, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	06.01.2019	CNR
Focus Group Recordings and Transcripts (This task is lead by EVAI, but CNR organized or moderated some focus groups, thus this dataset is stated in addition to the focus group recordings of with master data of EVAI)	Focus Group	2.1	Folder of PDF, DOCX, MP4, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	06.01.2019	CNR
Dissemination and communication plan First version (This deliverable is directly managed by CSIC, but some of procedures and disseminations go through CNR in particular due to the coordination role. Accordingly, an additional dataset with CNR is stated for this deliverable).	Deliverable	8.2	PDF, DOCX, PPT	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.07.2018	CNR

Exploitation plan - First version (This deliverable is mutually managed by FCA and CNR. Accordingly, an additional dataset with CNR is stated for this deliverable).	Deliverable	8.3	PDF, DOCX, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.02.2019	CNR
Risk Management Plan - First version (to be updated every 6 months until M18) (This deliverable is directly managed by AVIC, but some of risks and mitigation plans go through CNR in particular due to the coordination role. Accordingly, an additional dataset with CNR is stated for this deliverable).	Deliverable	9.3	PDF, DOCX, PPT, ELSX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	01.06.2018	CNR
Analysis and specifications of re-use value chains	Deliverable	1.2	PDF, DOCX, PPT	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	30.11.2018	CNR
Analysis and specifications of re-use value chains	Deliverable	1.5	PDF, DOCX, PPT	Public	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal, PreziSlide	30.04.2019	CNR
Detailed engineering of processes and technologies performed by Smart Mobile Modules (SMMs)	Deliverable	4.1	PDF, DOCX, PPT	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	30.06.2019	CNR
Detailed engineering of processes and technologies for batteries re-use, remanufacturing and recycling	Deliverable	5.1	PDF, DOCX, PPT	Confidential	Project SharePoint, Internal CNR SharePoint, CNR internal	30.06.2019	CNR
Prototype drawings	Deliverable	3.3	DOCX, CAD	Confidential	CNR internal	31.07.2019	CNR
Sustainable Mobility; Multi-National Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis of Consumers' Drivers and Barriers	Conference Paper/Publication	WP1	PDF, DOCX	Public	SDEWES2019 Conference Platform, Conference Proceedings, Internal CNR, Internal LIU	09.10.2019	CNR
Lithium-Ion Batteries towards Circular Economy: a Literature Review of Opportunities and Issues of Recycling Treatments	Conference Paper/Publication	WP1	PDF, DOCX	Public	SDEWES2019 Conference Platform, Conference Proceedings, Internal CNR, Internal LIU	09.10.2019	CNR
Requirements for generalization of the approach to EU industry	Deliverable	1.4	DOCX	Public	Project SharePoint, Zenodo	01.03.2019	FCA, CNR
New smart products concepts definition	Deliverable	3.2	DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint	30.04.2019	FCA, CNR
Exploitation planning and implementation	Deliverable	8.3	DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint	31.05.2019	FCA, CNR

Business Plan-New B2C Service that leverages on the recovered parts and materials provided by OEMs and Fleet companies	Document (E-VAI Contribution)	8.3	PPTX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, EVAI internal	22.05.2019	E-VAI
E-vai-T 2.1 Deliverable CarE Service-20190517-b01 – Draft Version	Document	2.1	DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, EVAI internal	07.06.2019	E-VAI
D2.1-Partner Presentation-Service model	Document	2.1	PPTX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, EVAI internal	07.06.2019	CNR/ E-VAI
E-vai-CarE-service-20190517-b01	Document	2.1	PPTX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, EVAI internal	07.06.2019	E-VAI
Co-design of customized mobility services and business models (B2C) – draft for partner’s review – First Version	Deliverable	2.1	DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, EVAI internal	9.08.2019	E-VAI
Co-design of customized mobility services and business models (B2C) – Final Version	Deliverable	2.1	PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, EVAI internal	31.08.2019	CNR/ E-VAI
Testing and validation of re-designed products concepts	Deliverable	3.4	PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, internally IMA, CSIC	30.11.2019	IMA
Technical requirements for software and hardware innovative solutions	Deliverable	1.3	PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, PROD internally	30.11.2018	PROD
Design of the CarE-Service ICT Platform	Deliverable	6.2	PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, PROD internally	31.08.2019	PROD
Analysis of alternative solutions - Part/Battery Marketplace module	Document	6.2	PDF, DOCX	Confidential	Project SharePoint, PROD internally	31.08.2019	PROD
8 Interviews of French users	Interviews	2.1	Docx	Confidential	Project SharePoint	24.07.2019	EVAI
Risk management	Deliverable	9.3	Docx	Confidential	Project SharePoint	30.11.2018	AVI / CNR
Risk management	Deliverable	9.3	Docx	Confidential	Project SharePoint	30.05.2019	AVI / CNR
Risk management	Deliverable	9.3	Docx	Confidential	Project SharePoint	30.11.2019	AVI / CNR
Risk management and identification of side-effects	Deliverable	2.3	Docx	Confidential	Project SharePoint	30.11.2019	AVI / CNR
Realization of product prototypes	Deliverable	3.3	Docx, Pdf	Confidential	Fraunhofer internally, Project SharePoint	31.08.2019	FhG

Detailed engineering of processes and technologies for metal parts re-use and recycling solutions	Deliverable	5.2	Docx, Pdf	Confidential	Fraunhofer internally, Project SharePoint	30.06.2019	FhG
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4. FAIR data

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

A DOI is assigned to datasets for effective and persistent citation when it is uploaded to the Zenodo repository. This DOI can be used in any relevant publications to direct readers to the underlying dataset.

Each dataset generated during the project is recorded in PDF file with a standard format and allocated a dataset identifier. The file will be hosted at the CarE project's SharePoint. This dataset information will be included in the metadata file;

- Project acronym
- Project full title
- Project ref. no.
- Description/ Name of the datasets
- Relevant deliverable
- Deliverable name
- Contractual date of delivery
- Actual date of delivery
- Type (Deliverable, publication, survey, paper, etc.)
- Format
- Master of Data
- Dissemination level (public/ confidential)
- Repository (-ies)
- DOI (only for public datasets)
- Author(s)
- Other contributors
- Abstract
- Keywords

4.2 Making data openly accessible

Each partner must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Results are owned by the partner that generates them. “Results” means any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights. Apart from the data sets specified that will be made open (public), other data generated in CarE-Service project should be kept confidential to avoid jeopardizing future exploitation.

All the partners must disseminate their results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, as soon as possible (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). A partner that intends to disseminate their results must give to the other partners at least 45 days advance notice, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate (Article 29.1, Grant Agreement).

The data are made available to the public in order to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data generated by the CarE-Service project. Therefore, all the generated data should be deposited in the Zenodo depository platform (a free repository hosted by CERN and available to all), which allows researchers to deposit both publications and data, in line with Article 29.3 of the Grant Agreement.

On Zenodo, all research outputs from all fields of science are welcome. In the upload form, the uploader chooses between types of files: publications (book, book section, conference paper, journal article, patent, preprint, report, thesis, technical note, working paper, etc.), posters, presentations, datasets, images (figures, plots, drawings, diagrams, photos), software, videos/audio and interactive materials such as lessons.

All metadata are stored internally in JSON-format according to a defined JSON schema. Metadata is exported in several standard formats such as MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema (according to the OpenAIRE Guidelines).

Files may be deposited under closed, open, or embargoed access. Files deposited under closed access are protected against unauthorized access at all levels. Access to metadata and data files is provided over standard protocols such as HTTP and OAI-PMH.

Metadata is licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata is exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested.

For the CarE-Service project, a Community project page on Zenodo has been created where partners can link their uploads: <https://zenodo.org/communities/careserviceproject/>

4.3. Making data interoperable

The CarE-Service project aims to collect and document the data in a standardized way to ensure that, the datasets can be understood, interpreted and shared in isolation alongside accompanying metadata and documentation. Widespread file formats will be generated to ensure the easy access, exchange and reuse of the generated data from other researchers, institutions, organizations, countries, etc.

Metadata are data which describe other data. Metadata files contain information about the documents you're going to upload. A metadata file will be created manually in a PDF file and linked within each dataset.

Dataset Identification Sheet	
Project acronym	CarE-Service
Project full title	Circular economy business models for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services
Project ref. no.	776851
Description/ Name of the datasets	Data Policy and Management Plan – First Version
Relevant deliverable	D9.4
Deliverable name	Data Policy and Management Plan – First Version
Contractual date of delivery	30.11.2018
Actual date of delivery	30.11.2018
Type (Deliverable, publication, survey, paper, etc.)	Deliverable
Format	DOCK, PDF
Master of Data	C-ECO
Dissemination level (public/ confidential)	Public
Repository (ies)	C-ECO internally, Project sharepoint, Zenodo
DOI (only for public datasets)	10.5281/zenodo.3363055
Author(s)	Bolech M., Georgopoulos K., Kuntz D., Wagner M.
Other contributors	All partners
Abstract	This report describes the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the CarE-Service Project. The report aims at establishing the policy framework for information management and confidentiality within the CarE-Service consortium, the members of the Consumers' and Stakeholders Committees, as well as external stakeholders.
Keywords	data management plan, data management, data protection, data privacy, data policy, DMP

Figure 4: Metadata pdf file

4.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

The datasets will be made available for reuse through uploads to the Zenodo community page for the project.

In principle, data which are characterized as “public” are uploaded on Zenodo after its submission and approval by EC without additional costs. All the research data are of the highest quality, have long-term validity and are well documented in order to allow other researchers the ability access and understand them after at least 5 years.

If datasets are updated, the partner that possesses the data has the responsibility to manage the different versions and to make sure that the latest version is available in the case of publicly available data. Quality control of the data is the responsibility of the relevant responsible partner generating the data.

The following naming for the titles is recommended to the partners when they upload a public deliverable on Zenodo is the following; CarE-Service Project – “deliverable title”, e.g. *CarE-Service Project - Data Policy and Management Plan - First Version* (Figure 5).

The screenshot shows the 'Basic information' section of a Zenodo upload form. The 'Title' field is highlighted with a red box and contains the text 'CarE-Service Project - Data Policy and Management Plan - First Version'. Other fields include 'Digital Object Identifier' (10.5281/zenodo.2062001), 'Publication date' (2019-03-18), and 'Authors' (Georgopoulos, Konstantinos; Kanti, Cornelia; Bokan, Michael; Vangel, Markus). The form also includes a 'Reserve DOI' checkbox and a 'required' dropdown menu.

Figure 5: Suggested way to give title to uploaded deliverables (screenshot, Zenodo)

5. Allocation of resources

There are no costs for making the data from CarE-Service project findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). The repository platform that is used is Zenodo, an interdisciplinary open data repository service maintained by CERN, which allows researchers to deposit both publications and data while providing tools to link them without any cost. Any other costs related to open access to research data in the CarE-Service project are eligible for reimbursement during the duration of the project under the conditions defined in the Grant Agreement, in particular Article 6.2 D.3, but also other articles relevant for the cost category chosen.

Circular Economy Solutions GmbH (CECO) is responsible to deliver the Data Management Plan for the CarE-Service Project in accordance with Task 9.4 for deliverable D9.4 (submitted in November 2019), and also for the updated deliverables D9.7 and D9.8.

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), the project coordinator, is appointed as data controller to demonstrate that the data subject has consented to processing of their personal data in all cases. Regarding the personal data that may be collected from the platforms of PROD and EVAI, the data processor/data protection officer in these companies will demonstrate to the project data controller the consent/assent of the data subjects as part of their online subscription process.

All the project partners should respect the policies set out the Data Management Plan. Datasets have to be created, managed and stored appropriately and in line with European Commission and local legislation. Dataset validation and registration of metadata and backing up data for sharing through repositories is the responsibility of the partner that generates the data in the Working Package.

The datasets in Zenodo are preserved in line with the European Commission Data Deposit Policy and complies with the European Commission Open Access Policy and Research Data Pilot. The data will be preserved indefinitely on the Zenodo repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

6. Data security

During the project, all the data are stored on the partner’s storage devices (internal servers, cloud, etc.). In the following table, there are the detailed storage information for the partners of the project.

Short name	Data storage methods
CNR	At CNR, all data related to the CarE-Service project are stored in the well-known repositories that can be accessed only with specific credentials and denies any access from unauthorized sources. In particular, all data are stored and managed through personal devices (administrated by institutional credentials), Dropbox and Microsoft SharePoint.
LIU	At LIU, all data related to the CarE-Service project are carefully and securely managed and stored on local and cloud repositories that cannot be accessed by unauthorized internal or external entities.
ENV	ENV possesses an internal server with a folder named “CarEServiceProject” with restricted access for the staff designed to the project. Internal server cannot be accessed out of the facilities.
PROD	Documentation related to the project is stored in Microsoft Sharepoint Online and access to the data is controlled and made accessible to Prodigentia employees on a need-to-know basis. Microsoft provides the highest standards in data security in the industry, including ISO 27001 certifications. Data stored in the ICT platform databases are stored i) at PROD office (test and development systems) in local servers, with restricted access, accessible only to the team allocated to the CarE-Service project ii) at qualified datacenters in Europe (test and production systems). The technology used by PROD to implement the ICT platform follows the best practices in information security, implementing data encryption for passwords, single-sign-on, account lockout, among others. Following the best practices in the industry, PROD contracts regularly qualified 3rd parties to audit the solutions developed by PROD, running black-box and white-box tests. Potential security flaws identified are mitigated ASAP according to its criticality.
CSIC	All data related to the CarE-Service project are stored in an internal server named “CarEService” with access only for authorized persons. Peer-reviewed publications will be also stored in an Open Access Repository “Digital CSIC”, as well as in Zenodo.
CECO	In CECO, all the related to the CarE-Service project data are stored on data repositories which are managed by the IT service of CECO (with no access from outside) and on Microsoft Office 365 cloud, hosted in Germany for sharing easily the data internally.
COBSER	At COBSER, all data related to the CarE-Service project are carefully and securely managed and stored on local repositories that cannot be accessed by unauthorized internal or external entities.
FCA	In FCA, all the data related to the CarE-Service project are managed and stored on local repositories; from 2019 there is also the possibility to store them in a Google Suite Platform cloud repository that cannot be accessed by unauthorized internal or external entities.
RAD	At RAD all data related to Car-E Service European project are managed and stored on local and GeoSharing Platform residing on the internal servers. Both local and GeoSharing Platform <u>are not accessible from the external networks and only</u> the people actively involved in the Car-E work group can manage, store and up/down-load the data files generated.
IMA	At IMA all documents and data related to the CarE-Service project are stored on special secured data repositories which are managed by the IT service of IMA. In addition,

	project specific disseminated information will be stored on the specified Zenodo data repository.
Fraunhofer	In Fraunhofer, the data are stored at the institute’s internal server. The server is protected by modern firewall and antivirus system managed by specialist for that. The data are located in an area reserved only for the project where the access is allowed only to those who work in this project (6 persons).
AVIC	AVIC possesses an internal server with a folder named “CarE-Service” with restricted access for the staff designed to the project. Internal server that cannot be accessed by unauthorized internal or external entities
CIA	CIA possesses an internal server with a folder for the CarE-service project with restricted access for the staff designed to the project. Internal server cannot be accessed out of the facilities.
EVAI	E-VAI possesses an internal server with a folder for the CarE-service project with restricted access for the staff designed to the project. Internal server cannot be accessed out of the facilities.
JRC	Data, documents and files are stored on the local server that can be only accessed internally. Possibility for sharing folders is available.

In accordance with Article 29, “Dissemination of results – Open access – Visibility of EU funding”, and with the aim to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data generated by the CarE-Service project, data related to “public” tasks and deliverables are archived and preserved in the Zenodo data sharing repository. The platform provides the option for open or restricted access to data regarding the dissemination level.

7. Ethical aspects

All the CarE-Service project partners must carry out the action in compliance with ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity) and applicable international, EU and national law. The partners must respect the highest standards of research integrity - as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (Article 34, Grant Agreement).

CarE-Service does not intend to collect, store and/or process sensitive data (health, genetic or biometric data). CarE-Service may collect, store and keep on track both “anonymously” and “non-anonymously” non-sensitive personal data. Non-anonymous personal data are collected only in case this is needed to achieve the targets of the project. In this case, with full freedom/awareness of the data subject is ensured. For this purpose, a dedicated space for the consent of data subject on the non-anonymous data collection is present in the designed consent forms (Deliverable 10.1).

CarE-Service may collect personal data from members of the consortium and other participants for several reasons as questionnaires or surveys, meetings, conferences etc., In all cases the partners must follow the standard procedure of getting authorization from the members to show and distribute the results, the videos the images etc. to the public.

In CarE-Service, the data collection as well as processing are fully based on consent/assent of the data subject. Regarding the general personal data collection within CarE-Service project, the data subjects’ consent/assent is given in the context of a written declaration (by signing the forms). The templates of the informed consent/assent forms are devised to be fully compliant with EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The informed consent form is written in English and also translated and available in four more languages (German, Spanish, Italian and French) (Deliverable 10.1, §3.1 and Appendix A1, B1, C1, D1).

CarE-Service partners must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at the time it is disclosed (“confidential information”).

References

“Defining a Winning GDPR Strategy Part 3: Identity and Access Management to the Rescue”, Sagara Gunathunga (14 February 2018):

<https://wso2.com/library/article/2018/2/identity-and-access-management-to-the-rescue/>

DMP online: <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

European Commission, “2018 reform of EU data protection rules”:

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/priorities/justice-and-fundamental-rights/data-protection/2018-reform-eu-data-protection-rules_en

European Commission, “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 - The FAIR Data Principles”, Version 3.0 (26 July 2016):

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf#page=10

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, Horizon 2020 Programme, “Guidance How to complete your ethics self-assessment”, Version 6.0, (23 July 2018):

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, “Guidance - How to complete your ethics self-assessment”, Version 6.0 (23 July 2018):

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf

European Commission, Research and Innovation, Participant Portal H2020 Online manual, Open access and Data management, Data management:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe):

<https://www.openaire.eu/>

OpenAIRE Horizon 2020 Fact Sheets, “Personal data and the Open Research Data Pilot” (April, 2017):

<https://www.openaire.eu/or-data-pilot-factsheet/download>

The FAIR Data Principles:

<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

Social media policy:

<https://safehouse-denver.org/about/privacy-notice-and-social-media-policy.html>

<https://obeck.eu/en/legal-issues/data-protection/privacy-policy-social-media.html>

Zenodo repository platform:

<https://zenodo.org/> <http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

